

PROGRESSIVE FAILURE OF NOTCHED AND REPAIRED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

There is a need to develop more accurate and cost effective damage tolerance assessment analysis methods and efficient repairs as increasingly large unitized composite parts are employed in aircraft structures. This presentation discusses the integration of some of the analytical and computational tools for quantitative damage tolerance assessment of composites based on progressive damage modeling. A range of progressive damage analytical techniques such as the material property degradation method (MPDM) and element-failure method (EFM) with various modern failure theories such as the recently-proposed multi-continuum theory (MCT) and micromechanics-based failure theory (MMF) can provide predictions of initial and ultimate failure of composite structures. Several examples of progressive failure analyses of conventional CFRP and hybrid composite structures with these tools are presented.

Keywords: Progressive failure, element failure method (EFM), micromechanics of failure (MMF), cohesive elements (CE), multi-continuum theory (MCT).

INTRODUCTION

The high strength- and high stiffness-to-weight ratios and corrosion resistant properties of fiber reinforced composites are increasingly important in the current global climate where environmental awareness, the need to reduce carbon footprint, efficiency and economic considerations are pressing issues. However, there is still a general lack of understanding and awareness among engineers of the potential of composites in the design and manufacture of better products. Understanding the mechanical behavior of composites, including the failure mechanisms and damage progression, forms the basis of sound design philosophy and damage tolerance methodologies. Analytical and computational tools are now being developed for advanced progressive failure analysis beyond first ply failure (FPF). These usually employ some form of material property or stiffness degradation method (MPDM) or the more recent element-failure method (EFM), with the failure driven by an appropriate criterion.

Two of the most recent failure theories intended for application to fiber-reinforced composites are the multi continuum theory (MCT) [1, 2] and the

micromechanics of failure (MMF) criterion [3, 4]. These new failure theories have important differences from some earlier failure criteria such as Tsai-Wu [5] because they incorporate aspects of micromechanics and differentiates between fiber- and matrix-dominated failure modes. Both the MCT and MMF evaluate composite failure based on constituent (fiber and matrix) stresses, but use different approaches to calculate the stresses. The MCT uses phase averaging, while the MMF uses stress amplification/ concentration based on representative cell models of matrix and fibers.

For progressive failure, both MCT and MMF may be readily implemented in finite element (FE) codes with MPDM [6-12] or EFM algorithms [13, 14]. In MPDM, certain material stiffness values are reduced when the composite is considered to have failed according to the corresponding failure mode, i.e. either matrix failure or fiber failure. This, in turn, requires the code to recalculate the element and global stiffness every time an element fails, a process that can be computationally expensive. Furthermore, by reducing the material properties, the global stiffness matrix may become ill-conditioned, so that a converged solution is not always assured. On the other hand, in EFM, instead of modifying the element and global stiffness matrices, failure is modeled by directly manipulating the nodal forces of the elements that contain the damage, thereby avoiding potential convergence problems.

In this paper, two examples of damage progression analysis are discussed: damage progression analysis in open hole tension composite laminates and analysis of composite damage and repair.

DAMAGE PROGRESSION ANALYSIS IN OPEN-HOLE TENSION COMPOSITE LAMINATES

In this study, a tensile loaded carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) composite plate with an open hole model is analyzed. The analysis was performed using finite element software Abaqus. User defined subroutine UEL was used to implement EFM-MCT and EFM-MMF. The composite plate is made of carbon/epoxy IM7/5250-4 composite laminate with stacking sequence [45/0/-45/90]_s; its properties are listed in Table 1. The size of the plate is 76.2 mm x 76.2 mm, and the diameter of the central hole is 19.05 mm. One of the main concerns in modeling damage progression using finite element method is the possibility of mesh dependency; hence, four different finite element meshes were analyzed and compared in this study. Figure 1 shows four different finite element meshes with 168, 400, 600 and 864 elements, respectively.

Table 1 Material properties of IM7/5250-4 composite system [15].

Thickness (mm)	0.125
Modulus in fiber direction E_1 (GPa)	172.4
Transverse moduli $E_2 = E_3$ (GPa)	10.3
Shear moduli $G_{12} = G_{13}$ (GPa)	5.52
Shear modulus G_{23} (GPa)	3.45
Poisson's ratios $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.32
Poisson's ratio ν_{23}	0.4
Longitudinal tensile strength X (MPa)	2826.5

Longitudinal compressive strength X' (MPa)	1620.0
Transverse tensile strength Y (MPa)	65.5
Transverse compressive strength Y' (MPa)	248.0
Shear strength $S_{12}=S_{13}$ (MPa)	122.0
Shear strength S_{23} (MPa)	122.0
Coefficient of thermal expansion in fiber direction α_1 (/°F)	-0.2×10^{-6}
Coefficients of thermal expansion in transverse directions $\alpha_2= \alpha_3$ (/°F)	13.7×10^{-6}
Temperature difference (°F)	-375

Figure 1 Finite element mesh open-hole tension specimen

Figure 2 Stress-strain curves from open hole tension analysis using EFM-MMF and EFM-MCT

The simulation results in the form of the nominal stress and strain curves from the four models are shown in Figure 2. The figure suggests that for a reasonably fine mesh, which includes mesh 2, 3 and 4, the stress strain curves are similar. This shows that the method used in this analysis, i.e. EFM-MMF and EFM-MCT, is relatively mesh independent. Furthermore, the ultimate tensile strength predicted by the simulation is within 10% error from experimental value of 397.1 MPa [15].

ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE DAMAGE AND REPAIR

In this study, damage progression analysis of undamaged, damaged, and repaired composite plates is performed. The analysis was performed with the commercial FE software Abaqus. The user-defined subroutine UMAT [16] was used for the material property degradation scheme (MPDM) based on the micromechanics

failure (MMF) criterion. In addition, cohesive elements [16-19] were used to model the adhesive layers between the repaired plate and the repair patch. Two types of composite plates were considered: hybrid carbon fiber reinforced plastic and glass fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP-GFRP); and hybrid CFRP-titanium (TiGr).

Analysis of hybrid CFRP-GFRP plates

Three models of hybrid CFRP-GFRP plates were analyzed: undamaged plate (no hole), damaged plate (modeled with a through circular hole), and repaired plate (with circular hole and a bonded patch). The plate is made of 3 plies of T700/EP (CFRP) and 4 plies of R-Glass GFRP composite with the stacking sequence [CFRP 0/GFRP 45/GFRP -45/CFRP 90/GFRP -45/GFRP 45/CFRP 0]. Table 2 shows the mechanical properties of T700/EP CFRP and R-Glass GFRP used in the models. The size of the plate is 500 mm x 500 mm, and the circular hole is 80 mm in diameter. Four plies of circular patch and filler material were used to repair the plate. The parent plate, repair patch and filler layers are modeled with shell elements. The plate, patch and filler layers are assembled using cohesive elements (Figure 3). The patch is made of two plies of hybrid T700/EP CFRP and R-Glass GFRP in an [CFRP 0/ GFRP 45/GFRP -45] arrangement, while the filler layers are made of the same laminate as the repaired plate. The sizes of the patch plies are 120 mm, 160 mm, 200 mm, and 240 mm in diameter, with the smallest sized ply at the bottom and successively overlaid with larger plies.

The models were loaded in tension in the horizontal direction. Progressive damage was modeled using MPDM and driven by the MMF theory, implemented via user subroutine UMAT [16] in Abaqus. The following assumptions were used for the material property degradation:

- Elastic constants E_{22} , E_{33} , G_{12} , G_{23} , and G_{13} of the composite material were reduced by 95% when the matrix in the composite fails.
- Elastic constants E_{11} , E_{22} , E_{33} , G_{12} , G_{23} , and G_{13} of the composite material were reduced by 95% when the fibers in the composite fails.

Figure 4 shows the overall stress-strain response of the three cases: CG1 is the undamaged virgin plate, with no holes; CG2 is the damaged plate with the damage represented by a through hole; and CG3 is the damaged plate with a filled hole and patched repair. As may be expected, the damaged plate CG2 has a lower overall stiffness than the undamaged one CG1. The stiffness of the repaired plate CG3, however, is slightly greater than that of the undamaged plate CG1, due to the additional material introduced by the patch repair.

The strength of the virgin plate (CG1) is determined by analysis to be about 962 MPa. The presence of damage (CG2) represented by the hole reduces the residual strength to only 507 MPa, a very significant decrease of 47 percent. However, the patch repair scheme partially restores the residual strength to about 794 MPa. This analysis is an example of how quantitative analysis can provide an estimate of the efficiency of a repair scheme even before the repair is carried out, saving time and trial by error. By varying the patch size and number of repair plies, it is possible to further restore the residual strength of the structure.

More details may be inferred from Figure 4. It is interesting to note that initiation (Point A₂) and progression of damage in the holed plate (CG2) occurs very early in the load history due to the stress concentration at the hole's edge. Both the

virgin and the repaired plates, on the other hand, exhibit much greater resilience against damage initiation (Points A₁ and A₃ are located at much higher loads). The ultimate failure of the virgin plate immediately follows the initiation of fiber-dominated failure (Point B₁). However, in the damaged and repaired plates, the initiation of fiber-dominated failure does not necessarily signal ultimate failure of the structure. Major load drops, however, occurs after significant fiber-dominated failures have occurred (points B₂ and B₃). The geometric features of repaired plates permit more complex damage and failure progression routes, providing the repaired structure with more damage tolerant characteristics. Ultimate failure in these plates would be reached when a sufficient number of fibers have failed. The analysis of the complex behavior would not have been possible without the analytical tools developed for progressive damage.

Table 2 Mechanical properties of T700/EP CFRP, R-Glass GFRP, and Titanium alloy

	T700/EP CFRP	R-Glass GFRP	Titanium alloy
Thickness (mm)	0.125	0.134	0.127
E_{11} (GPa)	142	54	110
$E_{22}=E_{33}$ (GPa)	7	9.41	110
G_{12} (GPa)	3	5.55	41.4
G_{23} (GPa)	2.5	3.0	41.4
ν_{12}	0.25	0.33	0.33
ν_{23}	0.4	0.4	0.33
α_1 ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	0.56	6.1	8
$\alpha_2 = \alpha_3$ ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	31.2	26.2	8
X (MPa)	2968	1900	1100
X' (MPa)	2423	800	1100
Y (MPa)	85	57	-
Y' (MPa)	316	145	-
S (MPa)	76	54	

Figure 3 Model of a CFRP-GFRP plate repaired with a patch of four plies and filler layers

Figure 4 Nominal stress – strain curves for CFRP-GFRP plates under tension

Analysis of hybrid CFRP-Titanium (TiGr) plates

A similar analysis was performed for plates made of TiGr, a hybrid composite. The TiGr plate is made of three plies of titanium alloy and four plies of T700/EP CFRP arranged in [Ti/0/90/Ti/90/0/Ti] configuration. Table 2 shows the mechanical properties of titanium and T700/EP CFRP used in this study. The damaged plate is 500 mm x 500 mm in size with a 80 mm diameter hole at the center. A circular titanium patch 1 mm thick and filler layers are used to repair the plate (Figure 5). The patch size is 160 mm in diameter. The filler layers are made of the same composite layup as the parent plate (TiGr). The plate, patch, and filler layers are modeled using shell elements and cohesive elements are used to connect the plate, filler layers and patch. In-plane tensile load is applied to the models. As with the CFRP-GFRP models, damage progression analysis was performed using Abaqus/Standard. User subroutine UMAT [16] was used to model material property degradation of the CFRP lamina in the TiGr and the MMF criterion was the failure theory chosen. The following assumptions were also used for the material property degradation scheme for the CFRP, i.e:

- Elastic constants E_{22} , E_{33} , G_{12} , G_{23} , and G_{13} of the composite material were reduced by 95% when the matrix in the composite fails.
- Elastic constants E_{11} , E_{22} , E_{33} , G_{12} , G_{23} , and G_{13} of the composite material were reduced by 95% when the fiber in the composite fails.

The Von Mises yield criterion with elastic-perfectly plastic behavior was assumed for the Titanium alloy layers.

Figure 5 TiGr plate repaired with a titanium patch and filler layers

Figure 6 shows the comparison of average stress-strain curves for the three models of TiGr. As in the previous CFRP-GFRP case, the highest residual strength of 1217 MPa is reached by the virgin undamaged plate (TiGr1). The damaged plate (TiGr2) shows the lowest strength of about 712 MPa, a knockdown of more than 41 percent. Repair with a titanium patch and filler layer (TiGr3), however, partially restores the strength to 1039 MPa.

Figure 6 Nominal stress-strain curves for TiGr plates

The mechanisms of progressive damage in the TiGr plates are however, markedly different from that of the pure CFRP-GFRP plates. The departure from linear behavior was triggered by the onset of yielding in the titanium layers and failure of composite matrix (Points Y1, A1, Y2, A2, Y3 and A3). Note that failure of composite matrix occurred at almost the same time as the yielding of titanium plies. It appears that

the repair does have a considerable influence on the post-yield behavior of the plate, which is dominated by the progressive failure of the CFRP plies. In all three cases extensive fiber-dominated failure marks the ultimate failure of the structure.

CONCLUSION

The application of element failure method (EFM) and material property/stiffness degradation method (MPDM) in conjunction with recent failure theories such as the multicontinuum theory (MCT) and the micromechanics of failure (MMF) criterion have been demonstrated in this paper. Combined with cohesive elements, these methods can be powerful tools to analyse damaged and repaired composite structures.

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